

PATIENTS' SATISFACTION WITH QUALITY OF NURSING CARE PROVIDED IN EMERGENCY DEPARTMENTS AT HAIL GOVERNMENTAL HOSPITALS IN SAUDI ARABIA

Bahia Glalal Abd El-Razik Siam^{1(a,b)*}, Amani Saidan Alshammari²,
Asmaa Mohamed Ali AlAbd^{3(a, b)}

^{1a} Assistant Professor of Medical-Surgical Nursing, College of Nursing, Hail University, Saudi Arabia.

^{1b} Assistant Professor of Medical-Surgical Nursing, Faculty of Nursing, Port Said University, Egypt.

² Master Degree in Emergency Nursing, College of Nursing, Hail University, Saudi Arabia.

^{3a} Assistant Professor of Mental Health Nursing, College of Nursing, Hail University, Saudi Arabia.

^{3b} Assistant Professor of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing, Faculty of Nursing, Benha University, Egypt.

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2530-7458>

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Abstract: Patient satisfaction affects clinical processes and patients' outcomes, the quality of nursing care is crucial in determining how the patients are satisfied with their hospital stay. This study aimed to assess patients' satisfaction with the quality of nursing care provided at emergency departments of King Khalid Hospital and King Salman Specialist Hospital in Hail, Saudi Arabia. A descriptive cross-sectional research design was utilized. Sample included all clients who received nursing care at previous settings and who agreed to participate. A self-administered online questionnaire consisted of two parts: Socio-demographic data sheet of the study subjects & the patient satisfaction with nursing care quality questionnaire (PSNCQQ). Results revealed that more than three quarters of the study subjects had high satisfactory scores regarding total quality of nursing care, the overall quality of the nursing care the patients received during stay in hospital was excellent. In conclusion, the patients were satisfied toward the nursing care provided, they recommended the previous hospital for family and friends.

Keywords: Emergency Departments, Patients' Satisfaction, Quality of Nursing Care.

1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of healthcare services is becoming a major concern in all countries, through improving performance to maximize the population health, effectively and efficiently, by doing the right thing, at the right time, in the right way, for the right person and having the best possible results, through well-managed hospitals and clinics^[1].

The patients' satisfaction with nursing care quality evaluates the met and unmet needs of patients, enables to identify the gap in nursing interventions and helps to uplift the care quality within the organization. Nurses are the health care providers who monitor and take care of the patients round the clock in a hospital, and they are the key members of health care team who facilitate the hospitalized patients to adapt^[2].

Patient satisfaction has been defined from different aspects, it is the degree of satisfaction according to medical services received in line with their preferences and expectations [3]. Swarup believed that patient satisfaction is the expectation of people toward the healthcare services for healthcare aspects and requirements as quality of life, disease and other aspects [4]. In addition, patients' unique perspective toward the satisfaction is filtered by healthcare services experience and evaluating the level to which healthcare services experience meets their needs [5].

Nursing is an art and science that is directed to keep the individual, family, community, and the population as a whole to be healthy by applying the principle of holistic care. Nurses who are working in hospitals are directed to promote comfort, provide a compassionate and respectful care to the client. In addition, nurses are the frontline professional groups involved in the direct patient care giver. In different healthcare systems mainly in hospital settings patients most likely meet up and spend the highest amount of time with nurses during their hospitalization [6].

Nursing care is one of the major components of healthcare services [7]. Patients' satisfaction considered as an indicator for health quality of care and important health outcome, it went through challenging transformations to meet that increased needs and demands of healthcare organizations' population [8]. Recently, patients' satisfaction with Emergency Department's services become one of the main criteria that detect the quality of services [9].

The influx of care workers has been for nurse staffing in Saudi Arabia, where diversity in the health care workforce has been expanding in recent decades. Despite the enormous contributions of nurses to Saudi Arabia's health-care system, it appears that their job performance is harmed by a variety of working conditions; however, they tend to persevere in providing safe and quality care, so patient satisfaction becomes a good indicator of quality in the health-care system and provides a means for quality improvement [10].

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

Numerous research have demonstrated the correlation between improved patient satisfaction and favorable medical outcomes. Persistent fulfillment with care may be a complex set of distinctive components, it is essential to look at the different measurements of basic, restorative nursing, and bolster administration [11].

A prospective study revealed that the patient with higher satisfaction had better quality of life. A systematic assessment of the evidence revealed that patient satisfaction was positively correlated with patient safety, clinical efficacy, adherence to advised care, and utilization of screening services. It was important to assess patients' satisfaction, some recommendations for improvement will be formulated based on the results. Therefore, this study was applied.

AIM OF THE STUDY:

This study aimed to assess patients' satisfaction with the quality of nursing care provided in emergency departments at Hail Governmental Hospitals, Saudi Arabia.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

1. What is the level of patients' satisfaction with quality of nursing care provided at emergency departments?
2. Is there a relationship between patients' satisfaction with the quality of nursing care provided and their sociodemographic characteristics?

2. SUBJECTS AND METHODS

RESEARCH DESIGN:

A descriptive cross-sectional research design was utilized in the current study

SETTING:

The study was carried out at the emergency departments of King Khalid Hospital (KKH) and King Salman Specialist Hospital (KSSH) in Hail city, Saudi Arabia.

SUBJECTS:

A convenient sample consisted of all available conscious patients (120) in one month duration who had received nursing care at the previous settings who agreed to participate in the study within the study period.

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TOOL FOR DATA COLLECTION:

A self-administered online questionnaire consisted of two parts:

Part I: The Socio-demographic characteristics of studied patients (age, gender, residence, marital status, educational level, and occupation).

Part II: The Patient satisfaction with nursing care quality questionnaire (PSNCQQ): Adapted from Laschinger ^[12], it is available for free in public domain, translated to Arabic language. The questionnaire consists of 19 items, plus 3 additional questions designed to measure satisfaction with the overall quality of care during the hospital stay.

Scoring system: A five point Likert scale (excellent, very good, good, acceptable, and poor). The scoring system for the answer ranged from “1” poor to “5” excellent. The total score ranged from (0-110), then categorized as follows: Satisfactory (if total score $\geq 75\%$ ” and unsatisfactory if $<75\%$ ”

Reliability of tool: Patient satisfaction with nursing care quality questionnaire Cronbach’s alpha coefficient were calculated and reflected high reliability (0.991).

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee for Bioethics Research in Hail Health (Ministry of Health H-08-L-074), and Hail Health Cluster. Furthermore, a written consent was obtained from the participants through a heading statement after explaining the aim of the study to patients, assured about the confidentiality of obtained data and only used for the purpose of the research. Patient had the rights to withdrawal from the research at any time without giving any reason.

DATA COLLECTION:

The researcher meet the patients in emergency unit explained aim of study then send google form to them to avoid biased answers. Data collection extended over a period of one month from the beginning of September 2021 to the end of September 2021.

STATISTICAL DESIGN:

Statistical presentation and analysis of the present study was conducted, using the mean, standard deviation and, one sample t- test, one way ANOVA used to compare means between groups. If $p < 0.05$ is considered significant and $p < 0.005$ highly significant.

LIMITATIONS:

Because of their advanced age, medical condition, or illiteracy, some of the study's participants may were unable to answer. Also, participants didn't reply despite of the researcher encourage them and sent message by WhatsApp. Furthermore, some participants may misinterpret the questions, that influence their answers and so they were excluded.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 shows that 65.1% of the study subjects received care from the King Khaled hospital and 34.1% from King Salman hospital, 86% of them were in age group from 20 to less than 40 years, 88% of them were females, 58% were singles and 72% of them were working.

Table 2 indicates that the mean scores of clients' satisfaction toward the quality of the nursing care provided ranged from “4.16 to 4.4”. In general, the highest percentage was for excellent response. 60% of the clients' reported that the overall quality of the nursing care they received during the hospital stay was excellent and they recommended the previous hospital for family and friends.

Table 3 reveals that there was a highly significant statistical difference in total satisfaction scores of the studied patients as regards to gender and occupation ($p < 0.005$).

Figure 1 shows that 76.7% of the clients were satisfied toward the total quality of nursing care provided.

Table (1): Sociodemographic Characteristics of the study Subjects (n=120)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Hospital		
King Khaled Hospital	78	65.8
King Salman Hospital	42	34.1
Age in years		
Less than 20	12	10.0
20-	86	71.7
≥ 40	22	18.3
Gender		
Male	32	26.7
Female	88	73.3
Marital Status		
Single	58	48.3
Married	56	46.7
Divorced	6	5.0
Widowed	0	0.0
Education level		
Primary	12	10.0
Secondary	16	13.3
Bachelor degree	92	76.7
Occupation		
Working	72	60.0
Not working	48	40.0

Table (2): Frequencies and Mean Scores of Patients' Satisfaction with Nursing Care Quality (PSNCQQ) by Items (n=120).

PSNCQQ Items		Satisfaction with the quality of Nursing Care					Mean Scores
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Acceptable	Weak	
Satisfaction							
1	How clear and complete the nurses' explanations about tests and treatments are and what to expect	64 53.3%	32 26.7%	18 15.0%	2 1.7%	4 3.3%	4.25
2	How did the nurses explain how to prepare for tests and operations?	70 58.3%	28 23.3%	18 15.0%	0 %0	4 3.3%	4.33
3	Nursing ready to answer your questions	66 55.0%	36 30.0%	14 11.7%	0 %0	4 3.3%	4.33
4	How well nurses communicate with patients, families and doctors	62 51.7%	32 26.7%	20 16.7%	2 1.7%	4 3.3%	4.22
5	Inform family or friends: how well the nurses helped them keep them informed of your condition and needs	68 56.7%	24 20.0%	18 15.0%	6 5.0%	4 3.3%	4.22
6	Involving family or friends in your care: how much they are allowed to help with your care	68 56.7%	28 23.3%	18 15.0%	4 3.3%	2 1.7%	4.30
7	Attention and Care by Nursing: You have been given respect; Friendliness and kindness	64 53.3%	32 26.7%	18 15.0%	0 %0	6 5.0%	4.23
8	Attention of the nursing staff: How often nurses have examined you and how well they have tracked your case	68 56.7%	30 25.0%	16 13.3%	2 1.7%	4 3.3%	4.30
9	Choose what you see Acknowledging your opinions: To what extent do the nursing staff ask you what you think is important and give you options?	72 60.0%	26 21.7%	16 13.3%	2 1.7%	4 3.3%	4.33
10	Considering your needs: Nursing staff ling to be flexible in meeting your needs	66 55.0%	28 23.3%	18 15.0%	2 1.7%	6 5.0%	4.22

11	Nursing daily routine: how much they have adjusted their schedules according to your needs	68 56.7%	32 26.7%	12 10.0%	6 5.0%	2 1.7%	4.32
12	Help: The ability of the nursing staff to make you comfortable and reassure you	64 53.3%	32 26.7%	18 15.0%	0 %0	6 5.0%	4.23
13	The nursing staff I answer your calls: How quickly can they help	64 53.3%	26 21.7%	22 18.3%	2 1.7%	6 5.0%	4.16
14	Skill and competence of the nursing staff: How well do skills, such as administering medications and handling intravenous administration, perform skills?	60 50.0%	38 31.7%	18 15.0%	0 %0	4 3.3%	4.25
15	Coordination of care: teamwork between nursing and other hospital staff who looked after you	72 60.0%	24 20.0%	18 15.0%	2 1.7%	4 3.3%	4.32
16	Comfortable atmosphere provided by the nursing staff: a measure of calm and serenity	64 53.3%	34 28.3%	16 13.3%	0 %0	6 5.0%	4.25
17	Privacy: Maintaining your privacy by the nursing staff	62 51.7%	36 30.0%	16 13.3%	4 3.3%	2 1.7%	4.27
18	Discharge instructions: How clearly and completely did the nursing staff tell you what to do and what to expect when you leave the hospital	64 53.3%	40 33.3%	12 10.0%	0 %0	4 3.3%	4.33
19	Post-hospital care coordination: the efforts of nursing staff to meet your needs after you leave hospital	70 58.3%	24 20.0%	20 16.7%	2 1.7%	4 3.3%	4.28
20	The overall quality of the nursing care you received during your hospital stay	72 60.0%	30 25.0%	14 11.7%	2 1.7%	2 1.7%	4.40
21	In general, would you say your health is:	68 56.7%	32 26.7%	16 13.3%	2 1.7%	2 1.7%	4.35
22	Based on the nursing care I received, I would recommend this hospital to my family and friends	72 60.0%	30 25.0%	14 11.7%	2 1.7%	2 1.7%	4.40

Figure (1): Total Scores of Patient Satisfaction with Nursing Care Quality (n=120)

Table (3): Relation between the Sociodemographic characteristics of the Patients' and their Total Satisfaction Scores toward the quality of Nursing Care Provided.

Variables	Total Satisfaction		Test (t/f)	P-Value
	Satisfactory (92)	Unsatisfactory (28)		
Hospital				
King Khaled Hospital	56	22	t=1.61	0.11
King Salman Hospital	36	6		
Age in years				
Less than 20	12	0	f=2.898	0.059
20-	60	26		
≥ 40	20	2		

Gender				
Male	28	4	t=2.908	0.005**
Female	64	24		
Marital Status				
Single	48	10	f=0.821	0.442
Married	40	16		
Divorced	4	2		
Education level				
Primary	12	0	f=1.089	0.340
Secondary	14	2		
University	66	26		
Occupation				
Not working	46	26	t=4.253	0.000**
Working	46	2		

** Highly significant

4. DISCUSSION

Patient satisfaction (PS) is a set of criteria of healthcare quality as seen as by patients that is influenced by a number of complex factors. Several factors must be coordinated in order to create an appropriate environment for the development and improvement of PS while respecting patients' rights in every way [13].

Regards to the sociodemographic characteristics of the study subjects; it was found that the majority of patients were females, aged between 20 and 40 years. More than one half of them were singles. Regarding educational level and working status; most of the patients had bachelor degree and were working. These findings go in the same line with similar studies which stated that more than half of the respondents were females, educated, and employed [14-16].

The results of the current study revealed that more than three quarters of patients had high satisfaction scores regarding total quality of nursing care provided, this result is supported by a similar study which found that the Overall patients' PSNCQQ scores ranged from 1–4.05, with an average score of 1.61 [17]. This demonstrated a high degree of satisfaction with nursing care. In addition, the satisfaction level toward governmental emergency department services in Medina city was relatively high [18]. Furthermore; a study carried out in India and in Netherlands reported a general high satisfaction rate [19, 20]. While these findings incongruent with another finding which stated low general satisfaction scores [21].

More than half of the studied patients reported that the overall quality of the nursing care they received during the hospital stay was excellent and they recommended the previous hospital for family and friends. This finding is similar with another study carried out in Saudi Arabia, which stated that 86% of the patients showed an overall satisfaction about the quality of nursing care provided [22]. These findings had proved that patient's satisfaction has emerged as a central focus of health care delivery in emergency departments in Saudi Arabia.

Concerning the relationship between the sociodemographic characteristics of the studied patients and their satisfaction with the quality of nursing care provided, the results of the current study shows that there were highly significant statistical differences in total satisfaction scores of the patients as regards to gender and occupation; as males and working patients were more satisfied. These finding is consistent with previous studies who stated that male patients were more satisfied compared to their counterparts [23, 24].

However these findings in contrast with another study finding which demonstrated that the patient satisfaction did not have any association with patient's demographic variables [25]. In addition; female patients were more likely to be satisfied in terms of general satisfaction and time spent with doctor [14].

5. CONCLUSION

This study concluded that more than three quarters of patients were satisfied toward the total quality of nursing care provided. There was a highly significant statistical difference in total mean satisfaction scores of the patients as regards to gender and occupation

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